

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 680556.

Horizon 2020

Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESS
SET UP

D3.2. Reference cases report

Deliverable Type: Public
Date: 01/02/2019
Distribution: WP3
Editors: BCNecologia
Contributors:

List of authors

Partner	Authors
BCNecologia	Jordi Abadal, Moisès Morató, Ander Bilbao, David Andrés, Antonio Tobella, Sergio Sánchez

Document history

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
16/09/2016	1	BCNecologia		Creation
12/11/2016	1	BCNecologia		1 st Draft
29/11/2016	1	BCNecologia		Final Version
18/10/2018	1	BCNecologia		Revision
01/02/2019	1	BCNecologia		Final Version

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to show the performance of CHESSE SETUP system for several types of building under different climate conditions. For each case, the system is evaluated (solar surface, storage capacity, and heat pump power) in order to optimize energy performance, technical viability and economic feasibility. The results of this report will be used during the exploitation of the project.

The first chapter shows a sizing of the system for different buildings typologies which have a high thermal and hot water demand (sports centre, hospital, hotel, retirement home...) in different climate zones in Europe. These general cases will provide an overall idea of how the system can be replicated in future projects.

The second chapter discusses how the system can be implemented in real study cases, where some of the partners are currently involved and are potential sites where CHESSE SETUP can be implemented in a near future. Next real cases those are included:

- A superblock located in Barcelona city (Poblenou Superblock)
- A residential block located in Barcelona city (Barcelona's Eixample Block)
- A Hospital in Vilafranca del Penedès, a peri-urban village in Catalunya (Alt Penedès Hospital)
- The new ecological neighbourhood of 500 dwellings located in Villeneuve-Tolosane (ZAC Les Fonses)

Finally, a preliminary system sizing for the three pilot cases is showed:

- The main office of Lavola Company in Manlleu,
- A swimming pool and sports centre in Sant Cugat del Vallès,
- Existing social homes owned by Corby Borough Council.

For every general and real study case, a template with the most relevant results and the information is included (a type of building, weather conditions, system sizing, energy performance, investment costs, etc).

The software specifically developed for CHESSE SETUP (D3.1. Simulation software) has been used for the system simulation. The software provides hourly simulation including energy demand, heat balances, water mass balances and efficiencies for all the components of the system (solar panels, heat pump, etc.). It also furnishes information about the energy costs, heat losses in all the components (pipes, water tanks, etc.), etc.

The annexes include a more detailed description of the simulation results.

2. GENERAL CASES

CHESSE SETUP is suitable for many types of buildings, but especially for those that have a high hot water demand, as it is nearly constant during the whole year, in contrast to heating demand with greater fluctuations from summer to winter. In that way, it's possible to reduce the seasonal storage system capacity and investment costs.

The types of building studied in this chapter are:

- Sports centre (with swimming pool)
- Hospital
- Hotel 4*
- Retirement home
- Multi-family housing
- Single-family house

Each building has been simulated for 6 different cities representing the main climate areas in Europe. Temperature and solar radiation are the main factors affecting energy demand and system performance (solar panels production, heat losses...).

Figure 1. Climate zones map in Europe – Font: BCNecologia

2.1. Climate conditions for each climate zone

Barcelona (Coastal Mediterranean): Dry and hot summers, with an average temperature above 15 °C, with humid and rainy winters and mild temperatures. Also, high solar radiation.

Figure 2. Temperature and solar radiation in Barcelona – Font: PVGIS © European Communities

Madrid (Continental Mediterranean): Elements of a continental climate with pronounced thermal amplitudes both daily and annually. Seasonally it can vary from mild winters and very hot summers to cold winters and mild summers, in the latter case with frost and snow. Also very high solar radiation.

Figure 3: Temperature and solar radiation in Madrid - Font: PVGIS © European Communities

London (Typical Oceanic): Characterized by mild temperatures and abundant rainfall because of the proximity to the ocean on the West coast. Winters are cold and cool, summers with a small annual thermal oscillation (10 °C average). Rainfall is abundant and well distributed, although with a maximum winter and solar radiation is low.

Figure 4: Temperature and solar radiation in London - Font: PVGIS © European Communities

Davos (Mountain): In the mountain, climate temperature decreases from 0.5 °C to 1 °C with each 100 meters higher, which increases the relative air humidity and rainfall. Cold winters and low temperate in summers. Solar radiation is low.

Figure 5: Temperature and solar radiation in Davos - Font: PVGIS © European Communities

Stockholm (Continental): Characterized by the contrast between rainfall, high summer temperatures, and dry winter cold. Solar radiation is relatively low.

Figure 6: Temperature and solar radiation in Stockholm - Font: PVGIS © European Communities

Berlin (Warm summer continental): Similar to continental but warmer summers and higher solar radiation.

Figure 7: Temperature and solar radiation in Berlin - Font: PVGIS © European Communities

2.2. Climate setting

Once solar radiation and temperature have been determined, it is necessary to define every single climate according to those parameters. The process consists of extracting minimum and maximum values for temperature (T^a_{max} , T^a_{min}) and solar radiation (Rad_{Max} , Rad_{Min}), which allow establishing maximum variation (ΔT^a_{max} , ΔRad_{max}). All these variables are defined as:

- T^a_{min} : Average temperature of colder months (January and February),
- T^a_{max} : Average temperature of warmer months (July and August),
- ΔT^a_{max} : $T^a_{max} - T^a_{min}$
- Rad_{min} : Average radiation of colder months (January and February),
- Rad_{max} : Average radiation of warmer months (July and August),
- Δrad_{max} : $Rad_{max} - Rad_{min}$

Figure 8: Climate setting based in minimum and maximum values for temperature and solar radiation – Font: BCNecologia

The following figure is a comparison between the 6 different climate zones used in the general case simulation:

Figure 9: Climate comparison for the 6 climatic zones – Font: BCNecologia.

The main purpose of defining this climate system is to establish a correlation between them. In that way, it is possible to determine how similar in percentage is one climate A to another climate B, based on temperature and solar radiation. In this case, the explanation is based on temperature values but the same process can be done for solar radiation values.

Figure 10: Correlation between 2 different climates A and B based in its temperature values – Font: BCNecologia

The following equation shows the correlation between two different climates A and B:

$$\text{Correlation} = 1 - \left(\frac{\Delta T_{\max} - \Delta T_{\min}}{\Delta T_{\text{abs}}} \right) \times 100$$

The following graphic represents the correlation between a reference city, Paris, and the 6 climate zone cities based on the two parameters: temperature (blue) and solar radiation (green). The result of combining both parameters is Global Correlation (red).

This system shows how different cities located in different climate zones (Paris, London, Berlin) have more than 75% of similarity according to temperature and solar radiation, even though they could seem really different due to other climate parameters (humidity, precipitation...).

Figure 11: % Correlation (temperature, radiation, global) between 6 general case study cities and Paris – Font: BCNecologia

2.3. General cases' template

First page: case description

The overall look of a general case template is divided into three main areas. The purpose of this first template is to describe the type of building to analyze as well as to set heating and hot water demand in the 6 climate zones already described.

- 1st area: General case description
- 2nd area: Partial and total energy demand (6 climate zones)
- 3rd area: Heating and Hot water demand (6 climate zones)

1st area

MIX RESIDENTIAL + OFFICE

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE 12.500 m²

NUMBER OF USERS 750

MAINTHERMAL USES Heating _ 10.000 m²
HWS _ 500 showers

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 45°C
HWS _ 60°C

2nd area

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	91	117	204	339	209	274
	kWh/year	418.000	527.953	917.750	1.525.550	939.553	1.223.443
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	173	185	201	233	208	220
	kWh/year	776.400	834.089	903.088	1.048.295	934.773	990.606
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	266	303	405	572	417	492
	kWh/year	1.194.800	1.362.042	1.820.837	2.573.845	1.874.326	2.214.049

3rd area

Additional notes

* In the Hospital considered, it is established an HWS demand of xx liters/person/day.
 * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of xx°C is considered.
 * The current heating technology considered is natural gas with a performance of xx%.

Figure 12: 1st-page overall look – Font: BCNecologia

1st area: General case description

This first part consists of a general description of the considered building. The template header is divided into 3 parts:

- Type of building (Sports centre, Hospital, Hotel 4*, Retirement home, Multi-family housing, Single-family house)
- Picture of building
- General information:
 - Building total surface in m² (this surface includes non-heated areas)
 - Number of users or beds, depending on the building type (this input is required to establish DHW demand)
 - Thermal uses (includes all the building elements requiring thermal energy demand)
 - Supply temperature (different temperature for DHW and heating)

General info

MIX RESIDENTIAL + OFFICE

Type of building

Picture of building

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS	
BUILDING SURFACE	12.500 m ²
NUMBER OF USERS	750
MAIN THERMAL USES	
Heating	10.000 m ²
HWS	500 showers
SUPPLY TEMPERATURE	
Heating	45°C
HWS	60°C

Figure 13: 1st-area General info – Font: BCNecologia

2nd area: Partial and total energy demand (6 climate zones)

In this second part, the thermal demand of the building will be set. This annual demand is composed of Heating and Hot water and varies depending on each climate zone. The values are expressed according to the building surface (kWh/m²/year) and in absolute terms (kWh/year).

ENERGY DEMAND

6 Climate zones

	Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental	
		City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
1. Heating	Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	93	157	204	339	209	272
	kWh/year	458.000	547.953	937.750	1.545.550	939.653	1.223.443	
2. DHW	HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	573	185	201	233	208	220
	kWh/year	776.400	834.089	903.668	1.048.295	934.773	990.606	
3. Total	Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	266	303	405	572	437	492
	kWh/year	1.104.800	1.362.042	1.820.817	2.573.845	1.874.386	2.214.049	

Figure 14: 2nd-area Energy demand info – Font: BCNecologia

3rd area: Heating and Domestic Hot Water demand (6 climate zones)

This final part consists of the graphic representation of the thermal demand expressed according to the building surface (kWh/m²/year) depending on each climate zone.

It is observed that DHW demand does not vary from one climate zone to another, unlike heating demand which substantially depends on the climate.

Figure 15: 3rd-area Heating and DHW demand info – Font: BCNecologia

Second page: proposal

The overall look of a proposal template is divided into two main areas. The purpose of this page is to present results in various forms: technical, energetic and economic. All this information is required to establish a comparison for the CHESSE SETUP system applied in a type of building in different climates.

- 1st area: Results, absolute values
- 2nd area: Comparative ratios

1st area

PROPOSAL						
Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	1.500	1.610	4.350	8.200	4.750	5.600
Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	1.604.352	1.815.008	2.732.806	4.714.657	2.980.921	3.646.368
Water tank volume (m ³)	2.800	4.200	7.800	9.800	9.800	12.500
Heat pump power (kW)	80	100	125	180	150	150
Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	196.480	227.500	286.200	405.000	301.350	359.640
Energy savings (kWh/year)	1.405.647	1.602.402	2.142.138	3.028.053	2.205.160	2.604.764
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	84%	83%	84%	84%	84%	84%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	78%	79%	82%	83%	82%	82%
Initial investment (€)	108.272	203.361	850.639	1.288.730	1.107.067	1.245.696
Economic payback (years)	3	4	14	10	17	3

2nd area

Figure 16: 2nd-page overall look – Font: BCNecologia

1st area: Results

This first part is a presentation of results for the described building in the six climate zones. Those results are also divided into 3 parts:

- Technical results:

- Includes solar panel surface (m²) and water tank volume (m³) to satisfy thermal demand in each climate zone.
- Solar thermal production (kWh/year) is also required.
- Energetic results:
 - This part analyzes the energetic sufficiency (%) that can be achieved after applying the CHESSE SETUP system. That sufficiency is divided into thermal and total (thermal + electrical).
 - Energy savings derived from that thermal solar contribution are also presented in kWh/year.
- Economic results:
 - In this part, energetic results are translated into economic data. For that purpose, the initial investment in euros must be known, including water tank construction, solar panel installation, water pump and the whole system required to satisfy that thermal demand.
 - Secondly, a survey of the price of each kWh in different countries (source: Eurostat) and the evolution of that energy price through years has been carried out, in order to establish economic savings and payback.
 - Economic payback has been calculated comparing CHESSE SETUP investment and operation costs with a conventional heating system based on gas boilers.

PROPOSAL							
Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental	
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
1. Technical info	Solar panel surface (m ²)	330	420	1.100	2.300	1.250	1.550
	Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	358.452	432.342	697.082	1.331.359	786.906	1.011.122
	Water tank volume (m ³)	1.100	1.600	2.400	3.300	3.000	3.800
2. Energy info	Heat pump power (kW)	30	35	45	45	45	45
	Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	46.620	56.805	79.470	117.640	81.600	101.560
	Energy savings (kWh/year)	311.529	369.978	556.299	852.806	571.170	707.729
	Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	82%	82%	83%	84%	83%	83%
	Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	46%	49%	58%	66%	59%	62%
3. Economic info	Initial investment (€)	389.950	540.897	875.296	1.273.950	995.479	1.169.385
	Economic payback (years)	10	11	15	10	-	9

Figure 17: 1st-page Results – Font: BCNecologia

2nd area: Comparative ratios

The goal of the second part is to analyze the results obtained in order to compare them easily in a graphic way. In this regard, two ratios are elaborated and presented with their climate dependent factors.

- 1st Ratio:

- This ratio compares the solar panel surface and building surface. The ratio expresses the surface of the solar panel in m^2 is required for every $100 m^2$ of the building.
- The climate factors analyzed are the annual average temperature “T” ($^{\circ}C$) and the total global horizontal solar radiation “R” ($kWh/m^2/year$) in each climate zone. Those are key factors determining solar panel surface. Values are expressed in percentage in the second axis of the graphic.
- 2nd Ratio:
 - This ratio contrasts water tank volume and solar panel surface. The ratio expresses the volume of the seasonal tank in m^3 is required for every $100 m^2$ of the solar panel.
 - In this case, the climate factors analyzed are the atmospheric temperature range “ ΔT ” ($^{\circ}C$) and the atmospheric radiation range “ ΔR ” (kWh/m^2). This climate variation from winter to summer has a strong influence on the volume of the seasonal tank. These variables are defined as:
 - ΔT : The difference between the values of the highest and the lowest monthly average temperature,
 - ΔR : The difference between the values of the highest and the lowest monthly total global horizontal solar radiation,

Figure 18: 2nd-page Comparative ratios – Font: BCNecologia

2.4. General cases' results

i
SPORTS CENTRE

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE 4.500 m²

NUMBER OF USERS 200

MAIN THERMAL USES Heating _ 4.000 m²
Pool _ 400 m²
HWS _ 50 showers

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 50°C
HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	93	117	204	339	209	272
	kWh/year	418.000	527.953	917.750	1.525.550	939.613	1.223.443
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	173	185	201	233	208	220
	kWh/year	776.400	834.089	903.068	1.048.295	934.773	990.606
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	266	303	405	572	417	492
	kWh/year	1.194.800	1.362.042	1.820.817	2.573.845	1.874.386	2.214.049

- * In the Sports centre considered, it is established a HWS demand of **25 liters/person/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **22°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL						
Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Conti-nental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Conti-nental oceanic	Continen-tal
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stoc-kholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	1.500	1.610	4.350	8.200	4.750	5.600
Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	1.604.352	1.815.008	2.732.806	4.714.657	2.980.921	3.646.368
Water tank volume (m ³)	2.800	4.200	7.800	9.800	9.800	12.500
Heat pump power (kW)	80	100	125	180	150	150
Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	196.480	227.500	286.200	405.000	301.350	359.640
Energy savings (kWh/year)	1.405.647	1.602.402	2.142.138	3.028.053	2.205.160	2.604.764
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	84%	83%	84%	84%	84%	84%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	78%	79%	82%	83%	82%	82%
Initial investment (€)	108.272	203.361	850.639	1.288.730	1.107.067	1.245.696
Economic payback (years)	3	4	14	10	17	3

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

i
HOSPITAL

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE 8.000 m²

NUMBER OF BEDS 120

MAIN THERMAL USES Heating _ 6.400 m²
HWS _ 120 showers

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 50°C
HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	109	138	239	397	245	319
	kWh/year	697.600	880.258	1.530.168	2.543.556	1.566.620	2.039.852
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	57	61	66	77	69	73
	kWh/year	456.000	489.882	530.395	615.691	549.017	581.809
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	166	199	305	474	313	391
	kWh/year	1.153.600	1.370.140	2.060.563	3.159.247	2.115.637	2.621.661

- * In the Hospital considered, it is established a HWS demand of **55 liters/bed/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **19°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL

Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	1.400	1.800	4.900	10.100	5.500	6.700
Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	1.517.456	1.955.959	3.078.414	5.815.571	3.445.569	4.360.615
Water tank volume (m ³)	4.500	6.400	10.200	15.100	12.900	16.800
Heat pump power (kW)	80	95	125	165	125	180
Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	215.360	243.010	344.500	508.035	352.625	448.740
Energy savings (kWh/year)	1.357.176	1.611.930	2.424.192	3.716.761	2.488.985	3.084.307
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	81%	82%	83%	84%	83%	83%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	59%	61%	72%	76%	72%	74%
Initial investment (€)	335.891	481.514	997.911	1.624.478	1.309.113	1.516.502
Economic payback (years)	9	10	15	10	19	3

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

i
HOTEL 4*

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE	4.000 m ²
NUMBER OF BEDS	125
MAIN THERMAL USES	Heating _ 3.750 m ² HWS _ 125 showers
SUPPLY TEMPERATURE	Heating _ 50°C HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	80	101	175	292	180	234
	kWh/year	300.000	378.551	658.042	1.093.846	673.719	877.230
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	43	46	50	58	52	55
	kWh/year	173.000	185.854	201.225	233.584	208.289	220.730
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	123	147	226	350	232	289
	kWh/year	473.000	564.406	859.267	1.327.430	882.008	1.097.960

- * In the Hotel considered, it is established a HWS demand of **70 liters/bed/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **22°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL

Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Conti- nental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Conti- nental oceanic	Continen- tal
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stoc- kholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	580	730	2.000	4.200	2.300	2.800
Solar thermal production (kWh/ year)	629.109	801.416	1.266.132	2.422.557	1.444.759	1.825.160
Water tank volume (m ³)	2.000	3.000	4.500	6.200	5.900	7.100
Heat pump power (kW)	30	35	50	70	55	70
Heat pump consumption (kWh/ year)	87.840	100.520	146.000	218.820	146.630	188.720
Energy savings (kWh/year)	556.471	664.007	1.010.902	1.561.683	1.037.656	1.291.718
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	81%	82%	83%	84%	83%	83%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	37%	40%	52%	60%	52%	56%
Initial investment (€)	294.489	409.602	674.810	990.568	886.980	965.952
Economic payback (years)	17	18	-	14	-	4

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

i
RETIREMENT HOME

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE 5.800 m²

NUMBER OF BEDS 200

MAIN THERMAL USES Heating _ 5.500 m²
HWS _ 200 showers

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 50°C
HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	83	105	182	303	186	243
	kWh/year	456.500	576.029	1.001.321	1.664.469	1.025.175	1.334.852
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	38	40	44	51	45	48
	kWh/year	218.000	234.198	253.566	294.343	262.469	278.145
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	121	145	226	353	232	291
	kWh/year	674.500	810.227	1.254.887	1.958.812	1.287.644	1.612.997

- * In the Retirement home considered, it is established a HWS demand of **55 liters/bed/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **19°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL						
Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Conti-nental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Conti-nental oceanic	Continen-tal
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stoc-kholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	820	1.050	2.700	6.300	3.300	4.100
Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	890.872	1.148.223	1.737.762	3.621.047	2.078.099	2.684.348
Water tank volume (m ³)	3.000	4.200	6.800	9.100	8.300	11.000
Heat pump power (kW)	60	60	75	100	80	90
Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	128.220	147.120	221.925	324.100	222.320	276.750
Energy savings (kWh/year)	793.529	953.208	1.476.338	2.304.485	1.514.875	1.897.643
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	81%	82%	81%	83%	83%	83%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	58%	61%	69%	75%	70%	73%
Initial investment (€)	370.762	471.003	793.486	1.242.448	1.051.694	1.218.917
Economic payback (years)	15	15	19	12	-	3

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

i
MULTI-FAMILY HOUSING

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE **8.000 m²**

NUMBER OF USERS **240**

MAIN THERMAL USES Heating _ 8.000 m²
HWS _ 100 units

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 50°C
HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	20	25	44	73	45	58
	kWh/year	160.000	201.894	350.956	583.384	359.317	467.856
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	13	14	15	18	16	17
	kWh/year	104.800	112.587	121.898	141.501	126.178	133.714
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	33	39	59	91	61	75
	kWh/year	264.800	314.481	472.854	724.885	485.494	601.570

- * In the Housing considered, it is established a HWS demand of **22 liters/person/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **20°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL						
Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	330	420	1.100	2.300	1.250	1.550
Solar thermal production (kWh/year)	358.452	432.342	697.082	1.331.359	786.906	1.011.122
Water tank volume (m ³)	1.100	1.600	2.400	3.300	3.000	3.800
Heat pump power (kW)	30	35	45	45	45	45
Heat pump consumption (kWh/year)	46.620	56.805	79.470	117.640	81.600	101.560
Energy savings (kWh/year)	311.529	369.978	556.299	852.806	571.170	707.729
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	82%	82%	83%	84%	83%	83%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	46%	49%	58%	66%	59%	62%
Initial investment (€)	178.110	289.313	497.012	694.042	607.084	688.129
Economic payback (years)	17	-	-	17	-	5

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

i
SINGLE-FAMILY HOUSE

BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS

BUILDING SURFACE 150 m²

NUMBER OF USERS 3

MAIN THERMAL USES Heating _ 150 m²

SUPPLY TEMPERATURE Heating _ 50°C
HWS _ 60°C

ENERGY DEMAND

Climate zone		Coastal Mediterranean	Continental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Continental oceanic	Continental
City		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
Heating demand	kWh/m ² /year	15	19	33	55	34	44
	kWh/year	2.250	2.839	4.935	8.204	5.053	6.579
HWS demand	kWh/m ² /year	12	13	14	16	14	15
	kWh/year	1.786	1.919	2.077	2.411	2.150	2.279
Thermal energy demand	kWh/m ² /year	27	32	47	71	48	59
	kWh/year	4.036	4.758	7.013	10.615	7.203	8.858

- * In the House considered, it is established a HWS demand of **30 liters/person/day**.
- * For heating demand calculation, a setpoint temperature of **20°C** is considered.
- * The current heating technology considered is **natural gas** with a performance of **85%**.

PROPOSAL

Climate zone	Coastal Mediterranean	Conti- nental Mediterranean	Typical oceanic	Mountain	Conti- nental oceanic	Continen- tal
City	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stoc- kholm
Solar panel surface (m ²)	5	6	17	33	18	22
Solar thermal production (kWh/ year)	5.399	6.636	10.431	19.118	11.398	14.426
Water tank volume (m ³)	14	22	35	46	44	55
Heat pump power (kW)	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.7	0.8
Heat pump consumption (kWh/ year)	721	844	1.154	1.760	1.233	1.537
Energy savings (kWh/year)	4.748	5.597	8.250	12.489	8.474	10.421
Thermal energy self-sufficiency (%)	82%	82%	84%	83%	83%	83%
Total energy self-sufficiency (%)	41%	45%	54%	62%	54%	58%
Initial investment (€)	1.974	3.608	8.195	12.595	10.605	13.154
Economic payback (years)	13	19	-	-	-	6

RATIO: Solar Panel Surface / Building Surface

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

2.5. General cases' summary

Hereafter has presented a summary of the general cases analyzed, representing 2 elements of the system, solar panel surface (m²) and water tank volume (m³) as well as the ratio between both of them.

Similarly, it's exposed another scenario where CHESSE SETUP system covers only 50% of thermal demand, in order to study the reductions required, especially to the seasonal storage system. It can be noticed how the reductions in solar panel surface are about 50%-60% while those related to the water tank volume are about 70%-80%.

The scenario covering 50% of thermal demand in the Sports Centre is relevant, being a case with similar HWS and heating demand. This peculiarity implies that the CHESSE SETUP system is covering mainly the HWS demand which is almost constant during the whole year. Then the demand seasonality is reduced and very small water tank volumes are required.

In this case, another strategy is adopted. The outlet temperature of solar collectors is reduced, increasing the solar thermal panels' efficiency. This implies that the solar surface is lower, but the seasonal tank higher as the storage temperature range is reduced. This is particularly interesting with the hybrid solar panels because their efficiency especially increases when they operate at lower temperatures, becoming the best alternative to that single case.

The scenario covering 50% of thermal demand in Single-family housing has not been calculated due to really low water tank volumes.

100% THERMAL DEMAND

SUMMARY SHEET

SOLAR PANEL SURFACE (x100m² building)

		TYPES OF CLIMATES					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	33,3	35,8	96,7	182,2	105,6	124,4
	Hospital	17,5	22,5	61,3	126,3	68,8	83,8
	Hotel 4*	14,5	18,3	50,0	105,0	57,5	70,0
	Retirement home	14,1	18,1	46,6	108,6	56,9	70,7
	Multy-family housing	4,1	5,3	13,8	28,8	15,6	19,4
	Single-family housing	3,3	4,0	11,0	22,0	12,0	14,7

SEASONAL STORAGE TANK VOLUME (x100m² building)

		TYPES OF CLIMATES					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	62,2	93,3	173,3	217,8	217,8	277,8
	Hospital	56,3	80,0	127,5	188,8	161,3	210,0
	Hotel 4*	50,0	75,0	112,5	155,0	147,5	177,5
	Retirement home	51,7	72,4	117,2	156,9	143,1	189,7
	Multy-family housing	13,8	20,0	30,0	41,3	37,5	47,5
	Single-family housing	9,3	14,7	23,3	30,7	29,3	36,7

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

		TYPES OF CLIMATES					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	1,9	2,6	1,8	1,2	2,1	2,2
	Hospital	3,2	3,6	2,1	1,5	2,3	2,5
	Hotel 4*	3,4	4,1	2,3	1,5	2,6	2,5
	Retirement home	3,7	4,0	2,5	1,4	2,5	2,7
	Multy-family housing	3,3	3,8	2,2	1,4	2,4	2,5
	Single-family housing	2,8	3,7	2,1	1,4	2,4	2,5

50% THERMAL DEMAND

SUMMARY SHEET

SOLAR PANEL SURFACE (x100m² building)

	TYPES OF CLIMATES						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	10,0	11,1	26,7	44,4	28,9	35,6	72%
Hospital	7,5	10,0	25,0	45,0	28,8	36,3	59%
Hotel 4*	6,5	7,8	20,0	37,5	25,0	30,0	58%
Retirement home	6,5	8,6	21,6	37,9	24,1	31,0	57%
Multy-family housing	1,9	2,1	6,9	10,6	6,9	8,8	56%
Red	58%	59%	59%	66%	60%	59%	

SEASONAL STORAGE TANK VOLUME (x100m² building)

	TYPES OF CLIMATES						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	1,1	4,4	40,0	17,8	71,1	106,7	82%
Hospital	8,8	15,0	27,5	12,5	43,8	62,5	80%
Hotel 4*	7,0	14,5	25,0	17,5	37,5	55,0	79%
Retirement home	10,3	20,7	29,3	17,2	39,7	62,1	76%
Multy-family housing	2,3	4,0	9,4	3,5	10,3	15,0	77%
Red	86%	82%	75%	91%	72%	67%	

RATIO: Water Tank Volume / Solar Panel Surface

	TYPES OF CLIMATES						Red
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	
Sports centre	0,1	0,4	1,5	0,4	2,5	3,0	35%
Hospital	1,2	1,5	1,1	0,3	1,5	1,7	53%
Hotel 4*	1,1	1,9	1,3	0,5	1,5	1,8	51%
Retirement home	1,6	2,4	1,4	0,5	1,6	2,0	45%
Multy-family housing	1,2	1,9	1,4	0,3	1,5	1,7	50%
Red	69%	58%	38%	72%	26%	16%	

Theoretical surface and volume

The final stage consists of obtaining a relation between solar panel surfaces, STE volumes, demand profiles, and weather conditions. That relation will be used in the software developed by BCNecologia. In order to achieve that goal, different parameters have been taken into account:

- Temperature (Temp),
- Radiation (Rad),
- Temperature range (DTemp),
- Radiation range (DRad),
- Thermal demand,
- Heating demand,
- HWS demand.

The methodology used has been summarized in the net scheme:

Figure 19: scheme of the methodology – Font: BCNecologia

Theoretical solar panel surface

The first step is to determine the parameters that define the solar panel surface.

The first impression is to link solar panel surface and thermal demand. In that case, we can define an equation with an accuracy of 90%. The relation between both elements is defined by the next equation:

$$\text{Solar panel surface (m}^2\text{)} = -510 + 0,00287 * \text{Thermal demand}$$

In order to improve the efficiency of the equation, thermal demand is divided into heating and domestic hot water demand. By that simple move, we can determine the importance of every single demand on the solar panel surface. In that case, the relation becomes more precise achieving an accuracy of 93%. The relation between elements is defined by the next equation:

$$\text{Solar panel surface (m}^2\text{)} = -477 + 0,0035 * \text{Heating demand} + 0,0014 * \text{HWS demand}$$

The final step to improve the efficiency of the equation is to introduce climate conditions, as temperature and radiation. In that case, different parameters have been related, such as HWS demand and radiation, with a final accuracy of 96%. The relation between elements is defined by the next equation:

$$\text{Solar panel surface (m}^2\text{)} = 831,4 + 0,00291 * \text{Heating demand} + 2,14 * \frac{\text{HWS demand}}{\text{Radiation}} - 95 * \text{Temperature}$$

The relation described in the previous equation is defined by the following graphic, representing the 36 general cases analyzed (in red) and the equation itself (blue line). The trend is clearly noticed and involves 96% of the cases, while few of them move away from that defined trend.

Figure 20: Solar panel surface (m²) / Theoretical surface (m²) – Font: BCNecologia

		CLIMATE					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	33,3	35,8	96,7	182,2	105,6	124,4
	Hospital	17,5	22,5	61,3	126,3	68,8	83,8
	Hotel 4*	14,5	18,3	50,0	105,0	57,5	70,0
	Retirement home	14,1	18,1	46,6	108,6	56,9	70,7
	Multy-family housing	4,1	5,3	13,8	28,8	15,6	19,4
	Single-family housing	3,3	4,0	11,0	22,0	12,0	14,7

Figure 21: Solar panel surface/building surface (x100) – Font: BCNecologia

Theoretical ratio volume/surface

In order to define the theoretical volume of the STE tank, the ratio relating STE volume and solar panel surface has been determined. In that case, the parameters that have been used to establish the connection are temperature, radiation, temperature range, and radiation range. The relation between elements is defined by the next equation:

$$STE \text{ volume (m}^3\text{)} / \text{Solar panel surface (m}^2\text{)} = -0,9175 + 0,00385 * \frac{\text{Temperature}}{\Delta\text{Temp}} + 0,0151 * \Delta\text{Rad}$$

The relation described in the previous equation is defined by the following graphic. The accuracy of the equation is 80%, even though it is clearly noticed that there are two cases distorting the final result. The analysis shows that those cases correspond to the Sports Centre in Barcelona and Madrid, with lower heating demand values in comparison to HWS demand, so that the required STE volume is much smaller.

Figure 22: $[STE (m^3)/Solar \text{ panel } (m^2)] / [Theoretical \text{ vol}/surf]$. 36 general cases – Font: BCNecologia

If those distorting cases are removed so that the analysis is focused on 34 cases instead of 36, the equation accuracy is much higher, up to 93%. In that situation the equation would be as follow:

$$STE \text{ volume (m}^3\text{)} / \text{Solar panel surface (m}^2\text{)} = -0,9168 + 0,0047 * \frac{\text{Temperature}}{\Delta\text{Temp}} + 0,0141 * \Delta\text{Rad}$$

Figure 23: $[STE (m^3)/Solar \text{ panel } (m^2)] / [Theoretical \text{ vol/surf}]$. 34 general cases – Font: BCNecologia

Distorting

Cases		CLIMATE					
		Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm
BUILDING TYPE	Sports centre	1,9	2,6	1,8	1,2	2,1	2,2
	Hospital	3,2	3,6	2,1	1,5	2,3	2,5
	Hotel 4*	3,4	4,1	2,3	1,5	2,6	2,5
	Retirement home	3,7	4,0	2,5	1,4	2,5	2,7
	Multy-family housing	3,3	3,8	2,2	1,4	2,4	2,5
	Single-family housing	2,8	3,7	2,1	1,4	2,4	2,5

Figure 24: Solar panel surface/building surface (x100) – Font: BCNecologia

Once the solar panel surface and the ratio between STE volume and solar panel surface have been established with accuracy higher than 93%, it is possible to set the STE volume required.

Those equations let us establish a pre-sizing of the main elements composing CHESSE SETUP system, depending on climate and thermal demand variables, and will be helpful in future phases when analyzing the possibilities to implement the system in other locations and building types.

3. REFERENCE CASES

The aim of this chapter is to evaluate the potential to implement CHES SETUP system in real study cases through different cities in Europe. Similarly, 3 pilot cases have been analyzed in order to obtain a pre-dimensioning of the various elements that compose the system.

The types of real cases studied are:

- District,
- Residential block,
- Sports centre,
- Hospital,
- Office.

The locations of those cases are:

- Barcelona (Spain)
- Vilafranca del Penedès (Spain)
- Toulouse (France)
- Manlleu (Spain)
- Sant Cugat del Vallès (Spain)
- Corby (England, UK)

Figure 25: Climate zones map in Europe – Font: BCNecologia

3.1. Reference cases' template

First page: case description

The overall look of a reference case template is divided into two main areas. The purpose of this first template is to describe the type of building, to analyze as well as to set thermal and total demand and consumption.

- 1st area: General case description
- 2nd area: Partial and total energy demand (6 climate zones)

1st area

2nd area

Figure 26: 1st-page overall look – Font: BCNecologia

1st area: General case description

This first part consists of a general description of the considered building. The template header is divided into 3 parts:

- General information:
 - Type of building, location.
 - Supply temperature (different temperature for DHW and heating).
- Overall description
 - Includes a brief description of the study case in order to understand its context and interactions.
 - Specific information of the case required to analyze the development of the system (number of housings, surface...).
- Energetic system
 - Summary of the energy technologies used in the project, energy sources and possible systems desired to implement.

Figure 27: 1st-area General case description – Font: BCNecologia

2nd area: Demand and consumption

In this second part, the demand and consumption of the building will be set. The demand, which values are expressed in absolute terms (kWh/year) and according to its surface (kWh/m²/year), is divided into four domestic uses:

- Hot Water,
- Heating,
- Cooling,
- Electricity (including domestic appliance, lighting...)

The second part represents the total consumption divided by the energy source, gas or electricity.

The final part constitutes a graphic representation of the monthly thermal demand, expressed according to the building surface (kWh/m²/year).

Figure 28: 2nd-area General case description – Font: BCNecologia

Second page: proposal

The overall look of a proposal template is divided into three main areas. The purpose of this page is to present results in various forms: technical, energy and economic. All this information is required to set the framework where the CHESSE SETUP system can be implemented.

- 1st area: Proposal
- 2nd area: Results (technical, energy, economic...)
- 3rd area: Graphics results (tank temperatures, system supply)

1st area

PROPOSAL

As the study case is located into a consolidated area, one of the project constraints is the solar panel surface as it can not exceed the roof surface. The report developed for the original competition established a maximum surface for solar panels of 2.700 m². The other constraint to implement the system into such a consolidated area may be the lack of space to set the Solar thermal water tank. The block structure with a huge hole in its interior ensures this required space.

2nd area

SYSTEM PARAMETERS	FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar pannels: 2.700 m² Yearly efficiency: 55% 1.104 kWh/m²/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 314.400 kWh/year 10,0 kWh/m²/year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Storage system: 8.000 m³ Max temperature: 80°C Average temperature: 42°C Min temperature: 15°C 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 487.800 kWh/year 15,5 kWh/m²/year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat pump: 200 kW Yearly COP: 4,2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.981.890 kWh/year 94,6 kWh/m²/year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermal self-sufficiency: 69,8% Total energy self-sufficiency: 28,4% 	
ECONOMIC DATA	ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial investment: 1.81 M€ Annual savings: 228.000 € / year Economic payback: 8 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CO₂ savings: 676 tn CO₂ / year Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 101 people Primary energy saving: 244 tep / year

3rd area

Figure 29: 2nd-Page Overall look – Font: BCNecologia

1st area: Proposal

This first part is a description of the most important information related to the system proposal, possible constraints due to the case attributes, which may emerge in the design and implementation phase.

PROPOSAL

As the study case is located into a consolidated area, one of the project constraints is the solar panel surface as it can not exceed the roof surface. The report developed for the original competition established a maximum surface for solar panels of 2.700 m². The other constraint to implement the system into such a consolidated area may be the lack of space to set the Solar thermal water tank. The block structure with a huge hole in its interior ensures this required space.

Figure 29: 1st-area Proposal – Font: BCNecologia

2nd area: Results

The goal of the second part is to present a holistic approach to the system. In order to simplify the process, the results have been separated into four groups:

- 1. System parameters:
 - Includes the characteristics of the 3 main elements of the system.
 - Solar panel: surface (constrained by the building surface), efficiency and annual production (kWh/m²/year).
 - Storage system: volume (constrained by the building dimensions), inlet and outlet temperatures.
 - Heat pump: power in kW and yearly COP.
- 2. Future thermal scenario:
 - Thermal consumption of the desired scenario is divided into three categories depending on the energy source (gas, electric and solar). The values are expressed in absolute terms and according to the building surface.
 - The capacity of the system to cover future consumption with solar energy or self-sufficiency. The adequacy will be calculated in order to cover both - thermal and total - energy consumption.
- 3. Economic data:
 - Includes the investment required to establish the system (price of solar panels, water tank, heat pump ...), as well as its construction.
 - The possible savings due to the consumption of clean and “free” solar energy, instead of traditional sources like gas or electricity. The price of gas has been considered, as well as its evolution over the years.
 - The payback in a number of years.
- 4. System benefits:
 - Environmental benefits due to CO₂ emission savings. Thermal consumption is considered to be supplied by gas, so its emission factor is 0,252 kg CO₂/kWh.
 - In order to set a more friendly comparison of the environmental results, the CO₂ emission of an average European person has been established (source: bancomundial.org). This way a comparison can be done between the total CO₂ savings and the equivalent number of people CO₂ emissions.
 - Finally, the final energy savings due to the system are compared to primary energy savings, in order to consider the benefits of consuming local energy where losses due to transport are minimized.

Figure 30: 2nd-area Results – Font: BCNecologia

3rd area: Graphics results

This final part is to establish a graphic comparison of the results obtained by applying the system. The values compared are divided into two groups:

- 1. Tank temperatures:
 - This graphic presents the comparison of both water tank temperatures used, the seasonal storage tank (in red) and the direct use tank (in purple) throughout one year.
 - It is clearly seen how the seasonal tank stores energy during the summer (up to 80°C) to give it in winter when the solar radiation is lower and thermal demand higher.
 - Direct use tank, in turn, presents a much stable temperature range between 60°C and 70°C.
- 2. Solar supply:
 - This graphic compares thermal consumption (in green) and solar production (in orange) throughout the year.
 - Thermal consumption is divided into three groups:
 - Consumption due to the auxiliary boiler. The boiler is activated when the energy of the seasonal tank can't supply the thermal demand. A clear connection can be established between this consumption and seasonal storage tank temperature.
 - Heat pump consumption of electricity, required to satisfy thermal demand and ensure energy flow between the seasonal storage tank and the consumption place.
 - Energy is taken from the seasonal storage tank to the direct use tank and consumption place.
 - It is clearly seen how both consumption and production evolution are inverted.

Figure 30: 3rd-area Graphics results – Font: BCNecologia

3.2. Reference cases' results

i
POBLENOU SUPERBLOCK

BUILDING TYPE:	District
COUNTRY:	Spain
CITY:	Barcelona
CLIMATE ZONE:	Mediterranean

CASE DESCRIPTION

The Superblock is a new model of mobility that restructures the typical urban road network. Superblocks are made up of a grid of basic roads forming a polygon, some **400 by 400 meters**, with both interior and exterior components. The interior (intervia) is closed to motorized vehicles and above ground parking, and gives preference to pedestrian traffic in the public space.

In the Poblenou neighbourhood an area of **16 ha, 3.335 homes, 6.252 inhabitants** and **9 public buildings** is going to be transformed as a superblock.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

The main technologies for heating and hot water production are **gas heaters** and **heat pumps**. Some of the new buildings are also connected to the **central district heating**, using the energy produced by waste incinerator plant. In the superblock, there are two schools equipped with thermal panels (20 m²).

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

In the Poblenou superblock there is **125.388 m²** of available space on roofs for installing solar panels. However only **16,8%** (21.073 m²) has the optimal conditions (solar exposure and roof characteristics) to install solar panels.
 In this area there is a central district heating. CHESSE SETUP system can be integrated with the DH system in order to significantly reduce water tank size.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

- Solar panels: 20.000 m²
Yearly efficiency: 55%
1.113 kWh/m²/year
- Storage system: 50.000 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 40°C
Min temperature: 15°C
- Heat pump: 5.000 kW
Yearly COP: 4

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Thermal self-sufficiency:	59,3%
Total energy self-sufficiency:	23,4%

ECONOMIC DATA

- Initial investment: 9,65 M€
- Annual savings: 1.031.267€ / year
- Economic payback: 9 years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

- CO₂ savings: 1.851 tn CO₂ / year
- Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 276 people
- Primary energy savings: 594 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i
BARCELONA'S EIXAMPLE BLOCK

BUILDING TYPE:	Block	
COUNTRY:	Spain	
CITY:	Barcelona	
CLIMATE ZONE:	Mediterranean	

CASE DESCRIPTION

Barcelona's Eixample Block is a pilot project developed in the urban structure and designed by Cerdà in order to stimulate building refurbishment involving energy efficiency. Barcelona's urban structure is ideal to replicate the model all over the city.

In this instance, there are **394 housing units** and **5 service blocks** with a total area of **31.500 m²**.

The project has been conceived as a participatory process, as neighbors are taking part in all phases.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Heating technologies, used in residential blocks, varies: gas boiler (46%), centralised heat pump (7%), electrical radiator (31%), butane gas stove (3%), individual heat pump (20%).

Barcelona's Eixample Block aims to **reduce energy consumption**, as well as to **produce clean energy** from photovoltaic panels.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

As the case study is located in a consolidated area, one of the project constraints is the solar panel surface as it can not exceed the roof surface. The report developed for the original competition defined a maximum surface for solar panels of **2.700 m²**.
 The other constraint of the system's implementation in such a consolidated area may be the lack of space to set the Solar thermal water tank. The block structure with a huge space in its interior block area ensures this required space.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

- Solar panels: 2.700 m²
Yearly efficiency: 55%
1.104 kWh/m²/year
- Storage system: 8.000 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 42°C
Min temperature: 15°C
- Heat pump: 800 kW
Yearly COP: 4,2

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Thermal self-sufficiency:	69,8%
Total energy self-sufficiency:	28,4%

ECONOMIC DATA

- Initial investment: 2.71 M€
- Annual savings: 205.808 € / year
- Economic payback: 14 years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

- CO₂ savings: 676 tn CO₂ / year
- Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 101 people
- Primary energy savings: 244 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i
ALT PENEDES HOSPITAL

BUILDING TYPE:	Hospital
COUNTRY:	Spain
CITY:	Vilafranca del Penedès
CLIMATE ZONE:	Mediterranean

CASE DESCRIPTION

Alt Penedès Hospital is the only public hospital in the Alt Penedès sub-region. It was opened in 1995, and it has 134 beds, 5 surgery rooms, emergency rooms, maternity unit and medical consultations.

The hospital covers a total area of **16.200 m²**. The hospital is divided mainly in two levels, therefore there is a big surface available for solar panel installation. Additionally, it has a large parking lot where storage solutions can be implemented. Veolia is currently in charge of the management of the facilities.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Heating and cooling demand is distributed throughout the hospital in a four pipe water system. DHW is also distributed in a flow and return piping.

DHW and heating demands are produced centrally in the boiler room by **two thermal oil boilers of 1.740 kW**. Currently, there aren't any renewable energy installations.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

A total area of **2.000 m²** has been calculated as an available roof surface suitable for installing the solar thermal panels. A storage tank volume of **6.000 m³** will be required for this surface, and the **57,3%** of the thermal energy demand will be supplied by solar energy. One of the main challenges is the implementation of the seasonal storage system in a consolidated urban area, which will require civil work in the area.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

- Solar panels: 2.000 m²
Yearly efficiency: 55%
1.105 kWh/m²/year
- Storage system: 6.000 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 42°C
Min temperature: 15°C
- Heat pump: 600 kW
Yearly COP: 4,2

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Thermal self-sufficiency: 51,2%
Total energy self-sufficiency: 19,9%

ECONOMIC DATA

- Initial investment: 2,14 M€
- Annual savings: 145.915 € / year
- Economic payback: 14 years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

- CO₂ savings: 483 tn CO₂ / year
- Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 72 people
- Primary energy savings: 174 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i

ECOQUARTIER ZAC LES FONSES

BUILDING TYPE: District

COUNTRY: France

CITY: Toulouse

CLIMATE ZONE: Mediterranean

CASE DESCRIPTION

ZAC Les Fonses is an ecological neighbourhood project in Toulouse (Villeneuve Tolosane). The plan is composed of 513 dwellings, as well as office, commerce and school blocks, summing up a total area of **40.950 m²**.

The location, situated next to high biodiversity areas, provides the project with **natural wealth**. BCNecologia was involved in the project by studying and proposing solutions to increase the sustainability of the neighbourhood.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Several alternatives for the energy supply in the neighbourhood were analysed (biomass district heating, geothermal energy, photovoltaic panels and conventional systems).

To reduce initial investment costs, it was decided to use individual natural gas boilers for each home.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

The available roof surface it's enough to supply all heating and hot water demand in buildings with CHESSE SETUP system. It will be required **3.400 m²** of solar thermal panels and a tank volume of **7.600 m³** to be installed. As it's a new urban development, alternative storage systems as ATES and BTES can be explored.

The heat pump will consume **222.200 kWh/year** achieving energy savings about 86% compared to a convectional system using natural gas.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Solar panels: 3.400 m²
Yearly efficiency: 51%
640 kWh/m²/year

Storage system: 7.600 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 50°C
Min temperature: 15°C

Heat pump: 400 kW
Yearly COP: 5,71

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

0 kWh/year
0 kWh/m²/year

222.200 kWh/year
5,4 kWh/m²/year

2.177.051 kWh/year
53,2 kWh/m²/year

Thermal self-sufficiency: 84,1%

Total energy self-sufficiency: 42,7%

ECONOMIC DATA

Initial investment: 2,39 M€

Annual savings: 68.982 € / year

Economic payback: - years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

CO₂ savings: 324 tn CO₂ / year

Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 48 people

Primary energy savings: 117 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i
ECOEDIFICI LAVOLA

BUILDING TYPE: Office

COUNTRY: Spain

CITY: Manlleu

CLIMATE ZONE: Mediterranean

CASE DESCRIPTION

LaVola's Headquarters, also known as Ecoedifici Lavola, built in 2005, is composed of **5 levels** and **1.432 m²**. It is located in the village of Manlleu, a rural area in the province of Barcelona.

It's the first building in Spain to obtain the **LEED GOLD Certification** in 2010.

Ecoedifici Lavola is one of the CHESSE SETUP pilots.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

The main technologies, used for heating and hot water production, are **gas heaters** and **heat pumps**. Also, various strategies (passive + active) have been developed in order to reduce energy consumption.

It should be noted that currently the Ecoedifici has **solar panels** to supply hot water demand and **photovoltaic panels** covering **15%** of the electrical demand.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

Roof space availability and seasonal storage tank implementation are limiting factors. A small scale pilot of **40m²** of solar thermal panels is proposed in this building. For this solar surface **120 m³** of seasonal storage system will be required. Alternatives and strategies to reduce tank size will be researched (the use of PCM's, integration with other sources or technologies, system management etc.).

Mainly as it's a **small scale pilot** that supposes higher costs for supplied MWh and higher thermal losses in the seasonal system, economic payback is higher than 20 years.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Solar panels: 40 m²
Yearly efficiency: 54%
1.057 kWh/m²/year

Storage system: 120 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 34°C
Min temperature: 15°C

Heat pump: 20 kW
Yearly COP: 3,57

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

52.200 kWh/year
63,1 kWh/m²/year

8.200 kWh/year
9,9 kWh/m²/year

42.274 kWh/year
51,1 kWh/m²/year

Thermal self-sufficiency: 26,9%

Total energy self-sufficiency: 13,4%

ECONOMIC DATA

Initial investment: 62.040 €

Annual savings: 2.162 € / year

Economic payback: - years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

CO₂ savings: 1,4 tn CO₂ / year

Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 0,2 people

Primary energy savings: 0,4 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i

SANT CUGAT'S SPORTS CENTRE

BUILDING TYPE:	Sports centre
COUNTRY:	Spain
CITY:	Sant Cugat del Vallès
CLIMATE ZONE:	Mediterranean

CASE DESCRIPTION

Next to the Sant Cugat City Council is located a sports centre with 4 facilities (3 pavilions, 1 swimming pool and a fitness room). It's one of the **CHESSE SETUP** pilots.

CHESSE SETUP is going to be designed to supply hot water and heating demands to the swimming pool and the fitness room, with a total surface of **3000 m²**. Swimming pools have high thermal demands.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Currently, the heating supply system is based on gas boilers. There are several inertial water tanks, which can be integrated in the system.

Also, there is a small solar thermal panel surface, which supplies part of hot water demand, but there is no available information about the energy production of solar panels.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

The main limiting factor for the sports centre is the **seasonal storage system space availability**. In the sports centre, two spaces, where a 600 m³ tank could be installed, have been identified. One of the challenges will be to install the tank in an existing building. Modular water tanks may be an option. For a 600 m³ water tank a **1.500 m²** of solar panels can be installed, achieving a thermal self-sufficiency of 66,8%. Sports centres and specially swimmingpools are **suitable buildings** for CHESSETUP, as they have a consistent thermal demand during the whole year. Economic payback is lower than 10 years.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

- Solar panels: 1.000 m²
Yearly efficiency: 56%
1.133 kWh/m²/year
- Storage system: 600 m³
Max temperature: 80°C
Average temperature: 30°C
Min temperature: 15°C
- Heat pump: 150 kW
Yearly COP: 3,52

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Thermal self-sufficiency: 59,6%
Total energy self-sufficiency: 44,8%

ECONOMIC DATA

- Initial investment: 0,57 M€
- Annual savings: 63.650 € / year
- Economic payback: 9 years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

- CO₂ savings: 234 tn CO₂ / year
- Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 35 people
- Primary energy savings: 82 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

i

LOW CARBON HOMES, CORBY PILOT

BUILDING TYPE: District

COUNTRY: England, UK

CITY: Corby

CLIMATE ZONE: Maritime

CASE DESCRIPTION

The Low Carbon Homes in Corby consists of 47 dwellings, with 31 houses (13 townhouses, 8 3-bedroom houses and 10 4-bedroom houses) and an apartment block with 16 flats. The whole plot has an approximate size of **10,122 m²**. It's one of the CHESSE SETUP pilots.

The Corby Pilot is also **part of the bigger Priors Hall Park urban development of 500 Ha** to extend Corby. Priors Hall Park will consist of around 5000 dwellings and include other features such as schools, shops and a medical centre.

ENERGY SUPPLY EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Low Carbon Homes is due to be built during next years. The goal is **NZEB homes** with no gas supply.

TOTAL ENERGY DEMAND

CURRENT TOTAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

MONTHLY THERMAL DEMAND (kWh)

PROPOSAL

Seasonal storage system will be underground, in an Earth Energy Bank (BTES) in which energy heats liquid pumped to underground with pipes. Each house will have its individual heat pump and solar system.

To supply the heat demand **600 m²** of solar thermal panels and an equivalent volume of **1.850 m³** of ground storage will be required. However, the plan for this pilot is to equip Low Carbon Homes with hybrid solar panels that will also produce the electricity for household consumption. The use of hybrid solar panels will mean larger solar panel surfaces and higher investment costs.

SYSTEM PARAMETERS

Solar panels: 600 m²
Yearly efficiency: 53%
66g kWh/m²/year

Storage system (BTES): 1.850 m³
Max temperature: 60°C
Average temperature: 37°C
Min temperature: 15°C

Heat pump: 100 kW
Yearly COP: 4,33

FUTURE THERMAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

55.000 kWh/year
8,6 kWh/m²/year

401.427 kWh/year
63,0 kWh/m²/year

Thermal self-sufficiency: 79,8%

Total energy self-sufficiency: 52,8%

ECONOMIC DATA

Initial investment: 0,52 M€

Annual savings: 12.026 € / year

Economic payback: - years

ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

CO₂ savings: 59 tn CO₂ / year

Equivalent to CO₂ emitted by 9 people

Primary energy savings: 59 tep / year

WATER TANKS TEMPERATURES (°C)

MONTHLY THERMAL SUPPLY (kWh)

3.1. Reference cases' summary

Reference cases size and type are very wide, from a single office building to a whole residential neighbourhood, from an existing sports centre with a swimming pool to a hospital. This large variety of typologies conditions energy demand as well as the parameters of the main elements of the system.

The next table summarizes the main characteristics of the 7 reference cases:

Case	Demand (kWh/year)	Solar surface (m ²)	Tank volume (m ³)	Thermal self-sufficiency (%)	Heat pump power (kW)	Investment (€)	Saving (€/year)	Payback
Poblenou superblock	60.475.206	20.000	50.000	59,3%	5.000	9.645.559	1.031.267	9
Barcelona's Eixample block	6.527.001	2.700	8.000	69,8%	800	2.714.373	205.808	14
Alt penedès hospital	4.200.000	2.000	6.000	51,2%	600	2.135.849	145.915	14
Ecoquartier ZAC Les Forses	2.693.372	3.400	7.600	84,1%	400	2.387.443	68.982	-
Ecoedifici Lavola	133.437	40	120	26,9%	20	62.040	2.162	-
Sant Cugat sport centre	1.837.479	1.000	600	44,8%	150	566.757	63.650	9
Low carbon homes in Corby	412.385	600	1.850	84,1%	100	521.538	12.026	-

Figure 32: Summary – Font: BCNecologia

In most cases, the main limiting factor is the roof surface availability to install solar panels. This constraint implies that self-sufficiency is never achieved in any of the reference cases studied. Hereunder is the graphical representation of the thermal self-sufficiency, clearly constrained by this parameter.

Figure 33: Thermal self-sufficiency of Reference cases – Font: BCNecologia

Another constraint noticed in the analysis phase is seasonal storage system construction, and can imply almost half of the investment costs, especially in existing buildings. Hereunder is the investment cost graphical representation of the three main elements of the system: solar panels (green), storage system (orange) and heat pump (blue).

Figure 34: Distribution of the investment costs of the reference cases – Font: BCNecologia

The economic payback is very large in Eco-quartier ZAC Les Forses (France) and Low carbon homes in Corby (UK) due to really low gas prices in those countries. Naturally, this fact increases the economic payback as it's calculated comparing the CHESSETUP with a conventional system base on natural gas boilers. Also for Ecoedifici Lavola payback is too large, as it's a small installation, increasing the thermal losses and specific costs. However, CHESSETUP system provides other benefits as sufficiency from energetic providers and consuming clean energy.

Finally note that the methodology used to calculate the investment cost sets aside some important parameters that should be taken into account in a future phase, as this study is an overall cost estimation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The CHESSE SETUP is a system designed to supply heating and DHW in buildings. In this report, it has been sized to supply 100% of the thermal demand in several building typologies under different climate conditions. The sizing has been done using specifically developed software for the project. The results should be taken as an approach, as a general idea of the system performance; for more precise sizing, specialized software should be used.

Also, it should be considered that there are many parameters and inputs which will affect the final result (solar panel efficiencies and operation temperatures, heat pump COP's, tank and pipes insulations, energy prices, investment costs...). Some of these values will be updated at the end of the project by using the outputs and results of future tasks of CHESSE SETUP.

Buildings located in colder locations with lower solar radiation will require larger solar thermal panel surfaces and seasonal storage tanks, as the energy demand is higher and the energy production for each solar panel is lower.

The relation between tank size and solar surface (or supplied demand) is a key factor and will influence the economic payback. It should be reduced as much as possible. There are several factors which affect this relation:

- 1) Weather seasonality: the solar radiation and temperature variability among the year affect significantly the relation between seasonal tank volume and solar surface. For example, in Madrid, where there is high weather seasonality, it's required a 3.8 m³ storage tank for each m² of solar panel, while in Davos it is required 1.2 m³ of the water tank.
- 2) The relation between DHW and heating demand: building with high DHW compared to heating demand requires a lower seasonal tank size, as DHW demand is more constant during the whole year. For example, a multifamily house in Barcelona requires 3.3 m³ of the seasonal tank for each m² of solar panel, while in a sports centre with swimming pool 1.9 m³ of the water tank is enough.
- 3) Solar panel temperature operation: in this report, it has been considered that in summer thermal solar panels produce hot water at 80°C. If this temperature is reduced, solar panels will increase their efficiency but the seasonal tank will achieve lower temperatures in summer, therefore larger tank volumes will be required. This issue will be explored in more detail in the next delivery 'D3.3. System configuration report'.
- 4) Climate conditions: this parameter also influences seasonal tank size. In colder places, heating demand increases more than DHW does. For example, in a multifamily house in Barcelona, DHW demand supposes around 40% of total thermal demand, while in Davos it supposes around 20%. That means that in Davos a higher tank size for each MWh of thermal demand will be required.

CHESSE SETUP can be very suitable for tropical areas, where solar radiation and temperature is very stable during the whole year. This can be applicable in buildings with hot water demand (sports centres, hospitals...) or in areas located in high altitude, which have heating demand even being near the equator. For example, in Quito, there are more than 2,000 sun hours and an average temperature of 13°C during the whole year.

In colder locations, and especially in buildings with high thermal demands, very large solar panels surfaces and water tanks are required. In some cases roof availability, space availability for installing the seasonal tank or investment costs will be a limiting factor that will prevent to supply the whole thermal demand. This can be appreciated in some of the reference cases. For example, in the Sant Cugat Sports Centre, the system has been sized to supply around 50% of thermal demand.

The integration of CHESSE SETUP with other energy sources as biomass, heat waste or geothermal energy can contribute to achieving NZEB for any weather and building typology. Also, the integration with other technologies as hybrid solar panels can contribute to producing both heating and electricity, consumed in the building. This is going to be explored in the next delivery 'D3.6. Integration with other sources and technologies report'.

In existing buildings, CHESSE SETUP system requires big investment costs and has high economic paybacks. For the economic balance estimation, the system has been compared with the implementation of a conventional heating system based on gas boilers. In the case of new buildings, lower economic paybacks are obtained. On one hand, because the civil work and system implementation are easier and lower investment costs are required. On the other hand, because in the economic study investment and maintenance of the conventional heating system is considered.

One of the main external factors affecting economic payback is the electricity and natural gas price. In countries with high natural gas prices and low electricity prices, like Sweden, the economic payback is much lower, as with CHESSE SETUP we are saving natural gas, but also the heat pump is consuming electricity. On the other extreme, there is Germany, with low natural gas prices and high electricity prices, obtaining very large economic paybacks.

The seasonal tank supposes more than half of the total investment system costs, so it's important to reduce tank size. As said before buildings with high DHW demand require lower tank size and therefore lower economic paybacks are obtained. One possibility is to size the CHESSE SETUP for supplying only DHW demand and a small part of the heating demand. For example, in a multifamily house located in Barcelona, tank size can be reduced by 4 times and the economic payback by 30% if the system is sized to supply 50% of the heating demand, instead of 100% of it.

As the last reflection, in temperate climates such as in Barcelona, it's possible to build houses with very low or no heating demand by using passive strategies (building insulation, double glazing windows...). It should be calculated if it's more profitable to invest in CHESSE SETUP or in implementing energy efficiency strategies. If this is the case, the system could be sized to supply the only DHW, with very small storage tanks and becoming much more profitable.

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6. ANNEXES

Heating Demand: Monthly distribution by climate conditions (HDD)

Month	Heating Demand distribution (% HDD)								
	Barcelona	Madrid	London	Davos	Berlin	Stockholm	Toulouse	Manlleu	Corby
Jan	20	20	14	13	17	16	19	19	16
Feb	17	17	14	13	16	16	17	17	15
Mar	15	12	12	11	13	14	12	14	12
Apr	11	9	10	9	9	10	9	10	10
May	5	4	7	6	4	5	5	5	6
Jun	0	0	4	5	0	0	0	0	3
Jul	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Aug	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Sept	0	0	4	5	3	5	0	0	4
Oct	4	5	8	7	8	8	7	6	8
Nov	12	14	12	11	13	12	13	13	12
Dec	17	19	14	13	16	15	18	18	14

Heating Demand: Monthly distribution by climate conditions (HDD)

Heating Demand: Monthly distribution by climate conditions (HDD)

Thermal Demand: Hourly distribution by building type

Hours	PERCENTAJE DISTRIBUTION (%)					
	MULTIFAMIL Y	SINGLE FAMILY	RETIREMENT HOME	SPORT CENTRE	HOSPITAL	HOTEL 4*
0	1	1	1	0	1	1
1	1	1	1	0	1	1
2	1	1	1	0	1	1
3	2	2	2	0	1	1
4	2	2	2	0	2	1
5	5	5	5	0	3	3
6	8	8	6	0	3	4
7	10	10	8	2	4	5
8	5	5	6	3	5	7
9	3	3	3	3	6	7
10	2	2	2	5	6	7
11	2	2	2	5	5	5
12	1	1	3	7	5	3
13	1	1	6	7	6	3
14	1	1	7	7	6	5
15	2	2	6	7	6	5
16	3	3	3	5	6	5
17	4	4	3	5	6	4
18	6	6	3	8	6	3
19	12	12	6	8	5	4
20	13	13	7	8	4	5
21	8	8	7	8	4	7
22	4	4	5	7	3	7
23	3	3	3	3	3	4

Thermal Demand: Hourly distribution by building type

